

**PROCEDEE DE TRADUCERE A NUMELOR PROPRII
DIN DICȚIONARUL LUI ANDREAS CLEMENS /
TRANSLATION TECHNIQUES OF PROPER NOUNS
IN ANDREAS CLEMENS' DICTIONARY**

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In Andreas Clemens’ bilingual dictionary (Buda, 1821) there are numerous proper nouns of different categories – anthroponyms, toponyms, theonyms, etc., in German and Romanian, giving the dictionary a distinctly didactic character. These nouns are culturally charged and indirectly provide information about the ethnic German community for which the dictionary is intended as a tool for learning Romanian. The Romanian equivalent is usually used to translate the German name, and this practice is carried out through various methods, such as word-for-word translation, explanatory translation, total equivalence or adapting the name into the Romanian language system. In this research, we aim to inventory and explain the translation methods that the author used to render the Romanian equivalents of proper nouns in the German part of the dictionary.